

Teachers' Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness: A Correlational Study

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Abstract- Emotional intelligence capacity of the teachers is the vibrant sign for their effectiveness in teaching. The major purpose of this study was to investigate relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence (EI) and their teaching effectiveness (TE). Descriptive-correlational design was adopted to conduct the study. The population is comprised of all the secondary school teachers of Lahore division. Multi-stage random sampling technique was used to select the sample. The sample of the study was consisted of 320 secondary school teachers. Two closed-ended questionnaires were used to collect the data. Pilot testing was conducted to ensure validity and reliability of the research instruments. Inferential statistical analysis techniques such as, Pearson r , independent sample t-test, one-way analysis of variance and linear regression were applied to analyze the data. The results revealed that there was a strong and positive significant correlation between teachers' emotional intelligence and teaching effectiveness. The results also reported that teachers' EI and TE were having significant difference in terms of their gender and teaching experience. The outcomes of linear regression also revealed that teachers' EI had a power of a reasonable power of predictability toward the teaching effectiveness in Lahore division, Pakistan

keywords: Emotional intelligence, Teaching Effectiveness, Secondary School Teachers

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a challenging process and it is a vast concept in teaching field. Competencies and skills through various attributes are part of effective teaching process and these elements are found in educational experts who are engaged in this field. Physical, mental, emotional and intellectual students' development depends upon teachers' these skills and competencies. Affective domain is cared by teachers for the students' development during teaching. Teachers' competencies depend on novel trends to managing of their emotions which put good impact in field of the teaching. Emotionally intelligent teachers show emotional skills and practices in their teaching. This makes their professional career successful. Emotionally intelligent teachers are described as thoughtful reflective figures of character and they are always flexible, as well as they are affirmative communicative figures. They are also optimistic with positive behaviors of creational habits in teaching activities. Strong emotional intelligence (EI) and effective teaching is necessary segment of teachers to flourish students' academic excellence (Soanes & Sungoh, 2019).

The educational system is based on the excellent teachers' excellent teaching in all over world. The academic success of students depends on teachers behaviors. EI means that it is the capacity of perceiving things, understanding phenomenon and evaluating various emotions (Fernandez-Abascal & Martin-Diaz, 2015; Vesely, Saklofske, & Leschied, 2013). EI is the ability to recognize feelings and emotions of one's own and others that make a distinction among them, and it guides one's thinking and actions (Gong, Chen, & Wang, 2019; Serrat, 2017). Pekaar, Van der Linde, Bakker, and Born (2017) elaborated about it that this is the emotional knowledge and this knowledge regulate different social and emotional behavior.

For teachers it is essential having emotional knowledge that is the foundation for positive relationships that also helps for good functioning in teaching learning process (Hargraves, 2017; Maamari & Majdalani, 2019), it increases professional performance of teachers, (Cejudo & López-Delgado, 2017), teaching and learning process (Allen, MacCann, Matthews, & Roberts, 2014), learners' school achievement (Becker, Goetz, Morger, & Ranellucci, 2014), teaching performance and job satisfaction (Cejudo & López-Delgado, 2017), reducing stress (Subalakshmi, Sunderaraj, & Manikandan, 2019), and the relational significance in educational context (Yin, Lee, Zhang, & Jin, 2013).

Less stress at work is due to high (EI) teachers than the less emotionally intelligent teachers. Kauts and Saroj (2010) stated in a study that teacher effectiveness could be increased by application of emotional intelligence. Six hundred secondary school teachers were sample of their study. They founded high EI teachers possessed less occupational anxiety but have good teacher effectiveness, and low emotional

intelligence teachers possessed more occupational anxiety but less teacher effectiveness. Emotional intelligence was helpful finally. High emotional intelligent teachers use more positive strategies during stress at school (Brackett, Palomera&Mojsa, 2010). Golema also tells that a person does not receive his ability based potential unless he owns his emotional capabilities to his job (Goleman, 1998).

Effective communication of teachers becomes more critical than their technical and organizational skills (Kauts&Saroj, 2010). Teachers' emotional intelligence plays vital role in school's "decision making, and leadership, relations and teamwork, commitment and creativity based on innovation" (Cooper, 1997, p.33). Student learning engagement, friendly environment in classrooms, promotion of productive ideas, their relations with students are due to only effective teachers' effective emotional intelligence (Sharma &Bindal, 2012).

EI has correlation with teacher effectiveness is proved by different empirical studies (Kaur, Shri, &Mital, 2019; Ramana, 2013; Salami, 2007; Soanes&Sungoh, 2019).Asrar-ul-HaqAnwar and Hassan(2017) explored the EI impact on teacher's job performance in the Pakistan, in a study in sample that was consisted on 166 teachers from universities from central Punjab -Pakistan, concluded that EI contains deep impact on the job performance of teachers. Bala (2017) held study on teacher effectiveness in relation to EI and the correlation between teacher effectiveness and EI.

Sekreter (2019) stated that EI is a vital indicator in the field of education. This vital indicator of TE inspected EI under teacher performance activity and it's relational to organizational productivity. EI skills and its impact on teacher's performance in teaching process were investigated, it was founded that effective teaching and good learning are correlated and these were vital parts of students' academic success. Therefore an affective teacher is needed to perceive students' emotional state in learning and its causes of their specific behavior during learning to create an ideal environment. This can encourage positive social learning interaction and active participation. Kauts and Saroj (2012) told high EI teachers contained less professional stress. Emotional intelligence proved helpful in reducing job related stress.

Vishalakshiin (2013) examined the "Teacher Effectiveness, Emotional Intelligence and Self-esteem of secondary school teachers". The findings were as firstly, male and female teachers of secondary school regarding different age groups; qualification and teaching experience are not with difference in teacher effectiveness. Secondly, there was clear difference between male and female teachers from secondary school regarding emotional intelligence and self Esteem. Thirdly, teachers from different age group and teaching experience were differing in emotional intelligence but not in self-esteem. On the basis of EI and Self-Esteem teachers of different qualifications were not differing.

Suvarna (2015) explored teacher effectiveness with its link to EI and also the personality type of science teachers of secondary school. Teachers showed medium level teacher effectiveness and EI. Bhagat (2016) held research "A Study of Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Teacher Effectiveness, Mental Health and Job Stress of Secondary School Teachers". A mean difference was noted in secondary school teachers' teaching effectiveness relating to high and low emotional intelligence. Mean difference in job stress had been noted among teachers of secondary school belonging to emotional intelligence, teaching experience, and gender.

EI capacity of the teachers is the vibrant sign for their effectiveness in teaching. Teacher attention for students produces effective results in learning in form of social skills as performance so it plays role in wellbeing of students regarding all aspects of students' life. Due to these factors a teacher looks effective in classroom strategies and activities which help to control their feelings for the goals and expectations. There was a need to conduct the study at secondary school level regarding EI and TE. So, the study was designed to see association between EI and TE in Lahore division.

Research Objectives

The study intended to achieve following objectives to

1. Investigate relationship between teachers' EI and TE.
2. Compare difference in teachers' EI and TE in terms of their gender and teaching experience.
3. Examine the effect of teachers' EI on TE.

Research Questions

Following were research questions of the study:

1. What is relationship between teachers' EI and TE?
2. Is there difference in teachers' EI and TE in terms of their gender and teaching experience?
3. What is the effect of teachers' EI on TE?

II. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used correlation research design to conduct the study. The study was non-experimental and descriptive in nature.

Population and Sampling Procedure

The population of the study was consisted of all the secondary school teachers of Lahore division. Lahore division is comprised of four districts. Multi-stage random sampling technique was used to select the sample. At the first stage, two districts were selected out of four districts of Lahore division by using simple random sampling technique. At the second stage, one tehsil was selected from each district from 2 selected districts of Lahore division. At the second stage, thirty girls' secondary and 30 boys secondary schools were selected randomly from one selected tehsil of each district. In this way, 60 secondary schools (e.g. thirty boys and 30 girls' schools) were selected through random sampling technique. Census technique was used in order to select the teachers. The major purpose of this technique was to get accurate picture of required data for current study. The sample of the study was comprised of 320 teachers working in selected schools at secondary level in Lahore division.

Research Instruments and Data Analysis

The researcher used two closed-ended self-report measures to collect the required data from the selected sample. Both instruments were adopted that were used in Pakistani context. Firstly, Bar-On (2002) "Emotional Quotient Inventory Short form" was adopted to measure teachers' EI level. It is a 5 point Likert type scale. It is consisted of six factors: "intrapersonal, interpersonal, stress management, adaptability, general mood, and positive impression". The reliability value of this scale was .92. Secondly, to explore TE, a 5 point Likert type scale was used. This scale was developed by Shahzad (2012) in Pakistani context. It constitutes 4 sub-variables for example: student-teacher relationship, supportive classroom environment, subject expertise & pedagogical knowledge and classroom management strategies. The reliability of this scale was 0.87. Data were collected by the researcher personally as well as by mail. Inferential statistical techniques such as Pearson *r*, one-way analysis of variance, independent sample t-test and linear regression were applied to analyze the data.

III. RESULTS

Table 1.

Correlation of Teachers' EI and TE

Variables	<i>n</i>	<i>r</i> -value	<i>Sig.</i>
Teachers' Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness	320	.884**	.001

p < .001 (2-tailed)

Table 1 indicated the outcomes of Pearson *r* that there was a strong and positive significant correlation between teachers' EI and TE, *r* = .884**, *p* < .001.

Table 2.

Relationship of EI factors and TE

Factors	1	2	3	4	5
Student- Teacher Relationship	1	.835**	.837**	.778**	.831**
Supportive Classroom Environment		1	.816**	.757**	.793**
Subject Expertise & Pedagogical Knowledge			1	.811**	.831**
Classroom Management Strategies				1	.818**
Teachers' EI					1

n = 320, ** *p* < .001 (2-tailed)

The above table reveals that the correlation between EI and TE. The factors of TE Student-teacher relationship (*r* = .831**), supportive classroom environment (*r* = .793**), subject expertise & pedagogical knowledge (*r* = .831**), classroom management strategies (*r* = .818**) were having strong relationship with EI. It is concluded that the dimensions of TE had positive and strong significant correlation with EI.

Table 3.*Independent Sample t-test by gender regarding the factors of EI and TE*

Sub Scales of EIT & TE	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P
Intrapersonal	Male	169	25.2899	3.59960	2.881	285.478	.001
	Female	151	23.9603	4.53855			
Interpersonal	Male	169	29.0118	4.80697	2.553	318	.289
	Female	151	27.6159	4.96503			
Stress Management	Male	169	17.8698	3.88766	3.792	317.924	.021
	Female	151	16.2980	3.52665			
Adaptability	Male	169	20.3254	3.33907	3.501	284.655	.001
	Female	151	18.8212	4.23176			
Self-motivation	Male	169	24.7396	4.10614	2.121	318	.124
	Female	151	23.7285	4.41955			
Positive Impression	Male	169	20.1183	3.58704	1.167	318	.130
	Female	151	19.6358	3.80961			
Student-Teacher Relationship	Male	169	25.2663	3.89216	2.760	296.017	.001
	Female	151	23.9470	4.57936			
Supportive Classroom Environment	Male	169	21.0592	3.61001	2.681	318	.068
	Female	151	19.9338	3.89815			
Subject expertise & Pedagogical Knowledge	Male	169	33.1065	5.17094	2.945	305.908	.028
	Female	151	31.3179	5.63841			
Classroom Management Strategies	Male	169	16.8876	2.60135	2.748	277.271	.001
	Female	151	15.9404	3.44912			

It is revealing from the above table 3 that the results of t-test regarding their gender with respect to the sub scales of teachers' EI such as: intrapersonal, stress management, adaptability had significant difference. T-test was also applied to compare mean scores of male and female TE such as: student-teacher relationship, subject expertise & pedagogical knowledge and classroom management strategies were having statistical difference. It is concluded that only three factors intrapersonal, stress management, adaptability had significance difference out of six factors of EI. It is also reported that three factors student-teacher relationship, subject expertise & pedagogical knowledge and classroom management had significant difference.

Table 4.*One way ANOVA on different dimensions of EIT and TE*

Sub- scales of EI and TE		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Intrapersonal	Between Groups	205.390	5	41.078	2.479	.032
	Within Groups	5202.160	314	16.567		
	Total	5407.550	319			
Interpersonal	Between Groups	285.699	5	57.140	2.409	.037
	Within Groups	7449.398	314	23.724		
	Total	7735.097	319			
Stress Management	Between Groups	17.494	5	3.499	.240	.945
	Within Groups	4584.253	314	14.600		
	Total	4601.747	319			
Adaptability	Between Groups	142.112	5	28.422	1.941	.087
	Within Groups	4597.610	314	14.642		
	Total	4739.722	319			
Self-motivation	Between Groups	237.905	5	47.581	2.665	.022
	Within Groups	5606.045	314	17.854		
	Total	5843.950	319			

Positive Impression	Between Groups	94.194	5	18.839	1.388	.229
	Within Groups	4262.978	314	13.576		
	Total	4357.172	319			
Student-Teacher Relationship	Between Groups	207.675	5	41.535	2.320	.043
	Within Groups	5621.713	314	17.904		
	Total	5829.388	319			
Supportive Classroom Environment	Between Groups	117.602	5	23.520	1.659	.144
	Within Groups	4452.145	314	14.179		
	Total	4569.747	319			
Subject Expertise & Pedagogical Knowledge	Between Groups	253.840	5	50.768	1.721	.129
	Within Groups	9262.110	314	29.497		
	Total	9515.950	319			
Classroom Management strategies	Between Groups	104.796	5	20.959	2.279	.047
	Within Groups	2888.075	314	9.198		
	Total	2992.872	319			

One way analysis of variance was applied on factors of EI and TE with respect to their teaching experience in years. Only three sub-scales of EI such as intrapersonal, interpersonal and self-motion out of six factors had significant difference. The results also showed that only two dimensions of TE student-teacher relationship and classroom management strategies was having statistical different. It is concluded that there was a statically significant difference between EI and TE with regard to their teaching experience.

Table 5(a).

Regression Analysis to identify the Predictive Power of EI and TE

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.884	.781	.781	7.20754

a. Predictors: (Constant), EI

Table 5(b).

ANOVA to determine the Significance Level of the Predictive Power of EI to assess TE

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	58991.344	1	58991.344	1135.571	.000
	Residual	16519.656	318	51.949		
	Total	75511.000	319			

a. Predictors: (Constant), EI

b. Dependent Variable: TE

Table 5(c).

Coefficients Model to fix the Predictive Power of EI for TE

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	B	B	Std. Error

1	(Constant)	5.121	2.664		1.922	.055
	Emotional Intelligence	.663	.020	.884	33.698	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TE

With regard to regression analysis for predicting TE in the above Tables, the results found that the contribution of EI was statistically significant in explaining the variance in TE ($B = .66$, $\beta = .88$).

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The current study was designed to relation between EI and TE of teachers in Lahore division. The outcomes of this study reported that teachers' EI and TE were having strong and positive significant correlation. The results of current study are supported by a number of empirical studies (Kaur, Shri, & Mital, 2019; Ramana, 2013; Salami, 2007; Soanes & Sungoh, 2019; Sekreter, 2019). On the whole in light of different researches regarding EI with effective teaching-learning process, it was concluded that EI of teachers' pays to the teacher effectiveness than any other factor. Teachers were more effective during teaching process with high level EI. Such teachers have the ability to plan the lessons according to the desired goals. They can also manage the classroom skills by better understanding of the students' individual differences in classroom.

The findings also revealed that EI is the strong predictor of TE. The results of study are also consistent with previous empirical studies such as Bhagat (2016), Hargraves (2017), Maamari and Majdalani (2019) and Sekreter (2019) in multiple contexts. The findings also reported that male and female teachers of secondary school regarding different age groups; qualification and teaching experience had difference in EI and TE. An affective teacher is needed to perceive students' emotional state in learning and its causes of their specific behavior during learning to create an ideal environment. Strong emotional intelligence (EI) and effective teaching is necessary segment of teachers to flourish students' academic excellence. The current empirical study recommended that courses should be included in teacher development programs related to EI. Teachers should be emotionally intelligent in the classroom scenario in order to achieve educational ends effectively.

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